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Taxonomical changes and comments on Palearctic and Oriental Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera)

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Abstract. Based on the study of primary type material, the following taxonomic changes in Palearctic and Oriental Galerucinae and Cryptocephalinae (Clytrini) are proposed: *Apophyllia* Thomson, 1858 = *Apophyllana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Galeruca* subgenus *Rhabdotilla* Jacobson, 1911, **stat. n.** = *Galemira* Beenen, 2003, **syn. n.**; *Aulacophora coffeae* (Hornstedt, 1788) = *Hoplasoma kelantana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Cassena collaris collaris* (Baly, 1879) = *Cneorane malayana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Coeligetes submetallica* Jacoby, 1884 = *Doryidella marginata* Medvedev, 2015, **syn. n.**; *Dercetina bicolora* (Medvedev, 2018), **comb. n.** (from *Doryidella*); *Dercetina bisbipunctata* (Medvedev, 2018), **comb. n.** (from *Doryidella*); *Galeruca* (*Rhabdotilla*) *sexcostata* Jacoby, 1904 = *Rhabdotilla rosti* Jacobson, 1911, **syn. n.**; *Menippus beeneni* Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012 = *Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Pseudocneorane apicalis* (Jacoby, 1884), **comb. n.** (from *Metrioidea*) = *P. fulvicornis* Medvedev et Romantsov, 2012, **syn. n.**; *Pseudocneorane grandis* (Allard, 1889), **comb. n.** (from *Metrioidea*); *Pseudocneorane molek* (Mohamedsaid, 1994), **comb. n.** (from *Metrioidea*); *Radymna rickmersi* (Weise, 1900) = *Galeruca* (*Haptoscelis*) *reitteri* Havelka, 1958, **syn. n.** *Galerucella flavidula* Reitter, 1913, **syn. n.** is removed from the synonymy with *G. tenella* (Linnaeus, 1760) and newly synonymized with *G. pusilla* (Duftschmid, 1825). Following new names are proposed due to homonymy: *Smaragdina vitalisi* **nom. n.** for *S. divisoides* Medvedev, 1988, nec *Gynandrophthalma divisoides* Chûjô, 1952 (now junior synonym of *Smaragdina fulveola* (Jacoby, 1890)); *Smaragdina gerhardi* **nom. n.** for *S. schereri* Lopatin, 2006, nec *S. schereri* Medvedev, 1970 (now *Afrophthalma schereri*); *Apophyllia skalei* **nom. n.** for *A. thoracica* (Medvedev, 2019), nec *A. thoracica* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963 (junior synonym of *A. flavovirens* (Fairmaire, 1878)); *Monolepta hagiangana* **nom. n.** for *M. bacboensis* Medvedev, 2015, nec *M. bacboensis* Medvedev, 2012. The spelling of *Smaragdina cribripennis* Tan, 1988 is fixed in accordance with the principle of the First Reviser.

Key words: taxonomy, new combinations, new names, new synonymy, Galerucinae, Cryptocephalinae, Clytrini.

Таксономические изменения и комментарии по палеарктическим и ориентальным Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera)

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Резюме. На основе изучения типового материала предложены следующие таксономические изменения для палеарктических и ориентальных Galerucinae и Cryptocephalinae (Clytrini): *Apophyllia* Thomson, 1858 = *Apophyllana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Galeruca* subgenus *Rhabdotilla* Jacobson, 1911, **stat. n.** = *Galemira* Beenen, 2003, **syn. n.**; *Aulacophora coffeae* (Hornstedt, 1788) = *Hoplasoma kelantana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Cassena collaris collaris* (Baly, 1879) = *Cneorane malayana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Coeligetes submetallica* Jacoby, 1884 = *Doryidella marginata* Medvedev, 2015, **syn. n.**; *Dercetina bicolora* (Medvedev, 2018), **comb. n.** (из *Doryidella*); *Dercetina bisbipunctata* (Medvedev, 2018), **comb. n.** (из *Doryidella*); *Galeruca* (*Rhabdotilla*) *sexcostata* Jacoby, 1904 = *Rhabdotilla rosti* Jacobson, 1911, **syn. n.**; *Menippus beeneni* Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012 = *Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* Medvedev, 2019, **syn. n.**; *Pseudocneorane apicalis* (Jacoby, 1884), **comb. n.** (из *Metrioidea*) = *P. fulvicornis* Medvedev et Romantsov, 2012, **syn. n.**; *Pseudocneorane grandis* (Allard, 1889), **comb. n.** (из *Metrioidea*); *Pseudocneorane molek* (Mohamedsaid, 1994), **comb. n.** (из *Metrioidea*); *Radymna rickmersi* (Weise, 1900) = *Galeruca* (*Haptoscelis*) *reitteri* Havelka, 1958, **syn. n.** *Galerucella flavidula* Reitter, 1913, **syn. n.** пересен из младших синонимов *G. tenella* (Linnaeus, 1760) в младшие синонимы *G. pusilla* (Duftschmid, 1825). Предложены новые названия для устранения омонимии: *Smaragdina vitalisi* **nom. n.** для *S. divisoides* Medvedev, 1988, nec *Gynandrophthalma divisoides* Chûjô, 1952 (сейчас младший синоним *Smaragdina fulveola* (Jacoby, 1890)); *Smaragdina gerhardi* **nom. n.** для *S. schereri* Lopatin, 2006, nec *S. schereri* Medvedev, 1970 (сейчас *Afrophthalma schereri*); *Apophyllia skalei* **nom. n.** для *A. thoracica* (Medvedev, 2019), nec *A. thoracica* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963 (младший синоним *A. flavovirens* (Fairmaire, 1878)); *Monolepta hagiangana* **nom. n.** для *M. bacboensis* Medvedev, 2015, nec *M. bacboensis* Medvedev, 2012. Написание *Smaragdina cribripennis* Tan, 1988 зафиксировано в соответствии с принципом первого ревизирующего.

Ключевые слова: таксономия, новые комбинация, новые названия, новая синонимия, Galerucinae, Cryptocephalinae, Clytrini.

In connection with the preparation of the new edition of the Palaearctic Catalogue of Chrysomelidae we present some new synonyms and nomenclatorial changes in Palaearctic and Oriental Galerucinae and Cryptocephalinae: Clytrini.

Material and methods

Photographs of the specimens (except Fig. 8) were taken with Canon EOS 550D digital camera with Canon MP-E 65 mm objective. Images of the same specimen at different focal planes were combined using Helicon Focus 7.1.6 software.

The examined material is housed in the following collections:

BMNH – Natural History Museum (London, UK, Michael Geiser, Maxwell V.L. Barclay);

HHCR – Hans Hebauer collection (Rain, Germany);

HNHM – Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary, Ottó Merkl);

JBCB – Jan Bezděk collection (Brno, Czech Republic);

MCZ – Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University (Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, Crystal Maier);

MFNB – Museum für Naturkunde, Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science (Berlin, Germany, Johannes Frisch, Joachim Willers);

MNHN – Museum National d'Histoire naturelle (Paris, France, Antoine Mantilleri);

NHRS – Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet Stockholm (Sweden, Johannes Bergsten);

NMEG – Naturkundemuseum (Erfurt, Germany, Matthias Hartmann);

RBCN – Ron Beenen collection (Nieuwegein, The Netherlands);

RMNH – Nationaal Natuurhistorische Museum ('Naturalis') (Leiden, The Netherlands, Fred van Assen);

ZIN – Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St Petersburg, Russia, Alexey Moseyko).

The exact label data are cited for all type specimens. Type localities are cited in the original spelling. Other comments and remarks are placed in square brackets: [p] – preceding data are printed, [h] – preceding data are handwritten, [w] – white label, [r] – red label, [b] – blue label, [g] – grey label.

Subfamily Cryptocephalinae

Tribe Clytrini

Smaragdina cribripennis Tan, 1988

Smaragdina cribripennis Tan, 1988: 322, 332 (original description).

Distribution. China (Xizang) [Tan, 1988].

Comments. The description of *Smaragdina cribripennis* contains two different spellings: *cribripenne* on pp. 322 and 323 and *cribepenne* on p. 332. We hereby fix *cribripennis* as the correct original spelling in accordance with the principle of the First Reviser, Article 24.2.3 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature [1999].

Smaragdina vitalisi nom. n.

Smaragdina divisoides Medvedev, 1988: 31 (original description).

Distribution. Vietnam [Medvedev, 1988].

Comments. *Smaragdina divisoides* Medvedev, 1988 from Vietnam is a homonym with *Gynandrophthalma divisoides* Chûjô, 1952 (now synonym of *Smaragdina fulveola* (Jacoby, 1890)) from Hubei and Taiwan. New name *Smaragdina vitalisi* nom. n. is proposed for *Smaragdina divisoides* Medvedev, 1988.

Smaragdina gerhardi nom. n.

Smaragdina schereri Lopatin, 2006: 593 (original description).

Distribution. China (Sichuan) [Lopatin, 2006].

Comments. *Smaragdina schereri* Lopatin, 2006 from Sichuan is a primary homonym with *Smaragdina schereri* Medvedev, 1970 (now *Afrophthalma schereri*) from Tanzania. New name *Smaragdina gerhardi* nom. n. is proposed for *Smaragdina schereri* Lopatin, 2006.

Subfamily Galerucinae

Genus *Apophyllia* Thomson, 1858

Apophyllia Thomson, 1858: 221 (original description).

Malaxia Fairmaire, 1878: 139 (original description).

Glyptolus Jacoby, 1884a: 62 (original description).

Malaxioides Fairmaire, 1888: 155 (original description).

Galerucesthis Weise, 1897: 296 (original description).

Bequaertinia Laboissière, 1922: 263 (original description).

Apophyllana Medvedev, 2019: 167 (original description), **syn. n.**

Comments. Medvedev [2019] distinguished *Apophyllana* from *Apophyllia* by glabrous elytra and by pronotum with shining sparsely punctate convexity along anterior margin. The only known specimen, holotype of *Apophyllana thoracica* Medvedev, 2019, is a female in very poor condition with missing abdomen and hind legs. The specimen was probably partly rotten and thus the elytral setation is scattered (but traces of setation are still visible). The pronotum with convexity along anterior margin is a character well known in many *Apophyllia* species. Because we do not see any characters useful for separation of both genera, we propose *Apophyllana* as a new synonym of *Apophyllia*.

Apophyllia skalei nom. n.

(Fig. 1)

Apophyllana thoracica Medvedev, 2019: 167 (original description).

Type material. 1♀, holotype (NMEG), "N-VIETNAM, Ninh Binh Prov., Cuc Phuong NP, N20°17'57.2" E 105°40'05.2", 270m, 22.5.-24.5.2015, leg. A. Skale" [w, p], "HOLOTYPE [p] *Apophyllana thoracica* [h] L. Medvedev [r, p]".

Type locality. "N-Vietnam, Ninh Binh Prov., Cuc Phuong NP, 20°17'57.2"N, 105°40'05.2"E".

Distribution. Vietnam [Medvedev, 2019].

Comments. *Apophyllana thoracica* is transferred here to the genus *Apophyllia* and thus becomes a homonym with *Apophyllia thoracica* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963 (synonym of *Apophyllia flavovirens* (Fairmaire, 1878)). New name *Apophyllia skalei* is proposed for *Apophyllana thoracica* Medvedev, 2019.

The species identity of *Apophyllia skalei* is not quite clear. The structure of pronotum with convexity along anterior margin is very similar for example to that of *Apophyllia brancuccii* Medvedev, 1998 collected on the same locality (series of 21 specimens in NMEG). However, the length ratio of antennomeres I to XI (14 : 6 : 8 : 12 : 10 : 10 : 10 : 9 : 9 : 9 : 12) is different to all *Apophyllia* species known to us. We are unable to assign *Apophyllia skalei* to any other *Apophyllia* species and we leave *Apophyllia skalei* as valid species.

Aulacophora coffeae (Hornstedt, 1788)
(Fig. 2)

Chrysomela coffeae Hornstedt, 1788: 5 (original description).
Hoplasoma kelantana Medvedev, 2019: 167 (original description), **syn. n.**

Type material. *Chrysomela coffeae*: not examined.

Hoplasoma kelantana: 1♂, holotype (NMEG), "MALAYSIA W., KELANTAN 40 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Berangkat Kampong Riek; 1100 m 15.v.-8.vi.2017 P. Cechovsky lgt." [w, p], "HOLOTYPUS Hoplasoma kelantana L. Medvedev" [r, p]; 1♀, paratype (NMEG), "MALAYSIA W., KELANTAN 40 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Berangkat Kampong Riek; 1100 m 15.v.-8.vi.2017 P. Cechovsky lgt." [w, p], "PARATYPUS Hoplasoma kelantana L. Medvedev" [r, p].

Type localities. *Chrysomela coffeae*: "Bantam" (= Java, Banten). *Hoplasoma kelantana*: "Malaysia W., Kelantan, 40 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Berangkat Kampong Riek".

Distribution. Widely distributed in Oriental region: South-East Asia, Sunda Land, Phillipines [Kimoto, 1989, 1990; Mohamedsaid, 2004].

Comments. Both examined specimens (holotype and paratype) of *Hoplasoma kelantana* undoubtedly pertain to common and widely distributed *Aulacophora coffeae*. Appropriate new synonymy is established.

Cassena collaris collaris (Baly, 1879)
(Fig. 3)

Euphyma collaris Baly, 1879: 457 (original description).

Cassena tonkinensis Weise, 1922: 128 (original description).

Solephyma tinkhami Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963: 663 (original description).

Cneorane malayana Medvedev, 2019: 167 (original description), **syn. n.**

Type material. *Euphyma collaris*: not examined.

Solephyma tinkhami: not examined.

Cassena tonkinensis: 1 ex., syntype (MFNB), "Central-Tonkin Chiem-Hoa Aug. Sept. H. Fruhstorfer" [w, p], "Cassena Tonkinensis m." [w, h], "Typus" [r, p], "Cassena tonkinensis W. [h] L. N. Medvedev det. 19 [w, p]"; 1 ex., syntype (NHRS), "Central-Tonkin Chiem-Hoa" [w, p], "Cassena tonkinensis m." [w, h] (NHRS).

Cneorane malayana: 1♂, holotype (NMEG), "MALAYSIA W., KELANTAN 40 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Berangkat Kampong Riek; 1100 m 15.v.-8.vi.2017 P. Cechovsky lgt." [w, p], "HOLOTYPUS [p] Cneorane malayana [h] L. Medvedev [r, p]".

Type localities. *Euphyma collaris*: "Assam" (by the title). *Solephyma tinkhami*: "Lao-kay, Sino-Vietnam border, Tonkin, N. Vietnam". *Cassena tonkinensis*: "Central Tonkin: Chiem-Hoa". *Cneorane malayana*: "Malaysia W., Kelantan, 40 km N of Gua Musang Berangkat Kampong Riek".

Distribution. South-East Asia, Peninsular Malaysia, southern China, Nepal, Bhutan [Maulik, 1936; Kimoto, 1989; Mohamedsaid, 2004; Medvedev, 2009; Beenen, 2010].

Comments. The holotype of *Cneorane malayana* undoubtedly pertain to common and widely distributed

Cassena collaris collaris. Appropriate new synonymy is established.

Coeligetes submetallica Jacoby, 1884

Coeligetes submetallica Jacoby, 1884b: 228 (original description).

Coeligetes wilcoxi Mohamedsaid, 1994a: 88 (original description).

Doryidella marginata Medvedev, 2015b: 327 (original description), **syn. n.**

Type material. *Coeligetes submetallica*: 1♂, syntype (MCZ, examined photo available at <http://mcbase.mcz.harvard.edu/SpecimenSearch.cfm>), "Dr. B. Hagen. Tandjong. Morawa. Serdang (N. O. Sumatra)." [w, p], "1st Jacoby Coll." [w, p], "Type [p] 18361 [r, h]"; 1♂, syntype (RMNS), "Coeligetes submetallica ♂ Jac." [b, h], "Dr. B. Hagen. Tandjong. Morawa. Serdang (N. O. Sumatra)." [w, p].

Coeligetes wilcoxi: not examined.

Doryidella marginata: not examined.

Type localities. *Coeligetes submetallica*: "Serdang (East Sumatra)" (by the title). *Coeligetes wilcoxi*: "Malaysia, Selangor, Bukit Belachan". *Doryidella marginata*: "S. Thailand, Phang-nga Prov., Thimung distr., 5 km S. Khao Lac, 08°36'N, 98°15'E".

Distribution. Peninsular Malaysia, Sumatra, Borneo [Bezděk, 2016], Thailand [Medvedev, 2015b].

Comments. Medvedev [2015b] described *Doryidella marginata* based on one female from South Thailand and the description was provided with the colour photograph of the holotype. One year later Medvedev [2016] published also the description of male from Peninsular Malaysia. Although we did not examine the holotype of *Doryidella marginata*, the study of photograph published in the description is sufficient to propose *Doryidella marginata* as a new synonym of *Coeligetes submetallica* (compare with recent revision of the genus *Coeligetes* Jacoby, 1884 by Bezděk [2016]).

Dercetina bicolora (Medvedev, 2018), **comb. n.**
(Figs 4, 5)

Doryidella bicolora Medvedev, 2018: 322 (original description).

Type material. 1♂, holotype (NMEG), "MALAYSIA W., KELANTAN 90 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Basor, 1700 m. Kampong Kubur Datu 10.iv.-5.v.2016 Petr Cechovsky lgt." [w, p], "HOLOTYPUS Doryidella bicolor [p] a [h] L. Medvedev [r, p]"; 1♂, 1♀, paratypes (NMEG), "MALAYSIA W., KELANTAN 90 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Basor, 1700 m. Kampong Kubur Datu 10.iv.-5.v.2016 Petr Cechovsky lgt." [w, p], "PARATYPUS Doryidella bicolor L. Medvedev" [r, p].

Type locality. "Malaysia, Kelantan, 90 km N of Gua Musang, Gunung Basor, Kampong Kubur Datu".

Distribution. Peninsular Malaysia [Medvedev, 2018].

Comments. *Doryidella bicolora* is a typical representative of the genus *Dercetina* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963 and seems to be closely related or conspecific with *D. variabilis* (Jacoby, 1886) distributed in Malaysia and Indonesia. The comparison with the type material of *D. variabilis* and with additional comparative material from whole distributional area is necessary to resolve its taxonomical position.

Dercetina bisbipunctata (Medvedev, 2018), **comb. n.**
(Figs 6, 7)

Doryidella bisbipunctata Medvedev, 2018: 322 (original description).

Type material. 1♂, holotype (NMEG), "MALAYSIA W., KELANTAN 90 km N of Gua Musang Gunung Basor, 1700 m. Kampong Kubur Datu 10.iv.-5.v.2016 Petr Cechovsky lgt." [w, p], "HOLOTYPUS [p] Doryidella bisbipunctata [h] L. Medvedev [r, p]"

Type locality. "Malaysia, Kelantan, 90 km N of Gua Musang, Guning Basor, Kampong Kubur Datu".

Distribution. Peninsular Malaysia [Medvedev, 2018].

Comments. As in preceding case, *Doryidella bisbipunctata* is a typical representative of the genus *Dercetina* and appropriate new combination is established.

***Galeruca* subgenus *Rhabdotilla* Jacobson, 1911, stat. n.**

Galeruca subgenus *Galemira* Beenen, 2003: 2 (original description), **syn. n.**

Comments. Beenen [2003] proposed the subgenus *Galemira* for *Galeruca sexcostata* Jacoby, 1904 (type species), *G. barovskyi* Jacobson, 1925, *G. himalayensis* Jacoby, 1896, and *G. subcostata* Beenen, 2003. Later [Beenen, 2008a], *G. holzschuhi* Mandl, 1981 was added to this subgenus too. Since *Galeruca sexcostata* Jacoby, 1904 proved to be a senior synonym of *Rhabdotilla rosti* Jacobson, 1911 (see below), *Galemira* Beenen, 2003 becomes a junior synonym of *Rhabdotilla* Jacobson, 1911.

Galeruca (Rhabdotilla) sexcostata Jacoby, 1904 (Fig. 8)

Galeruca sexcostata Jacoby, 1904: 405 (original description).

Rhabdotilla rosti Jacobson, 1911: pl. 59, **syn. n.**

Type material. *Galeruca sexcostata*: 1♂, lectotype (BMNH), "Type H. T." [circular label, borders red], "Lidder 1100" [w, p], "Jacoby Coll. 1909–28a" [w, p], "*Galeruca 6 costata* Jac." [b, h], "SYNTYPE" [circular label, borders blue], "*Galeruca sexcostata* Jacoby LECTOTYPE design. R. BEENEN 2002"; 1♂, paralectotype (BMNH), "Lidder 1100" [w, p], "Type" [r, p], "*Galeruca 6 costata* Jac. Type" [b, h], "Andrewes Bequest. B. M. 1922–221." [w, p], "SYN-TYPE" [circular label, borders blue], "*Galeruca sexcostata* Jacoby PARALECTOTYPE design. R. BEENEN 2002".

Rhabdotilla rosti: 1 ex., syntype (ZIN, photograph of this syntype was studied), "Kashmir" [w, h], "Rhabd. rosti K. Rost 1906" [w, h], "Т. Якобсонъ." [w, p], "Zoological Institute RAS (St.Petersburg) Зоологический ин-т РАН (г. Санкт-Петербург)" [w, p].

Type localities. *Galeruca sexcostata*: "Lider, Cashmere". *Rhabdotilla rosti*: not stated in the original publication, "Kashmir" based on the locality label.

Comments. Jacobson [1911] presented a picture of a species he named *Rhabdotilla rosti*, but did not publish a description. According to the Article 12 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature [1999] this name is available. The depositary of type specimen(s) was unknown, and also the type locality and species identity have stayed a mystery [Mandl, 1986, Beenen, 2008a]. Recently, Alexey Moseyko, the curator in ZIN, discovered three specimens that are to be regarded as syntypes. Two of them are from Semenov's collection and one is from Jacobson's collection (Fig. 8). It is evident that this is *Galeruca sexcostata*. From the labels it becomes clear that the syntypes of *Rhabdotilla rosti* have been collected in Kashmir, which is part of the realm of *Galeruca sexcostata*.

Galerucella (Neogalerucella) pusilla (Duftschmid, 1825) (Figs 9, 10)

Galeruca pusilla Duftschmid, 1825: 230 (original description).

Galerucella flavidula Reitter, 1913: 140 (original description), **syn. n.**

Type material. *Galeruca pusilla*: not examined.

Galerucella flavidula: 1♂, syntype (HNHM), "Turkestan, Aulie Ata" [w, h], "Holotypus [red letters, p] 1912 *Galerucella* (s. str.) *flavidula* Reitter" [w, h, label with red borders], "*flavidula* m Aulie" [partly illegible, w, h], "Coll. Reitter" [w, p]; 2♂, 6♀, syntypes (HNHM), "Turkestan, Aulie Ata" [w, h], "Paratypus [red letters, p] 1912 *Galerucella* (s. str.) *flavidula* Reitter" [w, h, label with red borders], "Coll. Reitter" [w, p].

Type localities. *Galleruca pusilla*: "Wien". *Galerucella flavidula*: "Transkaspien: Aulie Ata".

Distribution. Widely distributed throughout Palaearctic region [Beenen, 2010].

Comments. *Galerucella flavidula* was treated as aberration of *G. tenella* (Linnaeus, 1760) by Ogloblin [1936]. All subsequent authors [e.g. Wilcox, 1971; Warchalowski, 2003, 2010; Beenen, 2010] listed *G. flavidula* as synonym of *G. tenella*. The examination of the type series deposited in HNHM and aedeagus (Figs 9, 10) showed that *G. flavidula* has to be removed from the synonymy with *G. tenella* and newly synonymized with *G. pusilla*.

Menippus beeneni Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012 (Fig. 11)

Menippus beeneni Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012: 5 (original description).

Pyrrhalta shaanxiana Medvedev, 2019: 166 (original description), **syn. n.**

Type material. *Menippus beeneni*: 1♂, paratype (JBCB), "CHINA, Shaanxi, 1500 m, Ging Ling Shan Mts., Hou Zen Zi vill., 26.vi.1998, 30 km SE of Taibal Shan Mt., O. Šafránek & M. Trýzna leg." [w, p], "*Menippus beeneni* Lee et al., n. sp. des. C.-F. Lee, 2011" [w, p], "PARATYPE" [pink label, p].

Pyrrhalta shaanxiana: 1♂, holotype (NMEG), "CHINA, 17.-22.VI. Shaanxi prov. 1991 Hua Shan peak env. 100 km E of Xi'an Z. Kejval lgt." [w, p], "*Pyrrhalta* sp.? det. A. Warchalowski" [w, p], "HOLOTYPUS [p] *Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* [h] L. Medvedev [r, p]"

Additional material. 1♂, 1♀ (JBCB), China, Sichuan prov., Qingcheng Mt., 30°53.770'N / 103°34.690'E, 725 m, 11–16.05.2017 (R. Ambrus); 1♂ (HHCR), 1♀ (RBCN), China, Henan prov., Funiu Shan, Baotianman, 33°31'N / 111°56'E, 1500–1750 m, 5.06.2009 (J. Turna).

Type localities. *Menippus beeneni*: "China, Shaanxi, Tsinling mts., Foping Nature reserve, 33°51'N, 107°57'E". *Pyrrhalta shaanxiana*: "China, Shaanxi prov., Hua Shan peak env., 100 km E of Xian".

Distribution. China: Shaanxi, Shanxi [Lee et al., 2012, Medvedev, 2019], Henan and Sichuan (our data).

Comments. The holotype of *Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* was compared with the paratype of *Menippus beeneni*. Because the aedeagi of both taxa are identical *Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* is proposed as new synonym of *Menippus beeneni*.

Monolepta hagiangana **nom. n.**

Monolepta bacboensis Medvedev, 2015a: 69 (original description).

Distribution. Vietnam [Medvedev, 2015a].

Comments. *Monolepta bacboensis* Medvedev, 2015 from Vietnam is a primary homonym of *M. bacboensis* Medvedev, 2012 from Vietnam and China (Yunnan). New name *M. hagiangana* **nom. n.** is proposed for *M. bacboensis* Medvedev, 2015.

Figs 1–7. Habitus of type specimens and aedeagus.

1 – *Apophyllia skalei* **nom. n.** (*Apophyllana thoracica* Medvedev, 2019, female, holotype); 2 – *Aulacophora coffeae* (Hornstedt, 1788) (*Hoplasoma kelantana* Medvedev, 2019, male, holotype); 3 – *Cassena collaris collaris* (Baly, 1879) (*Cneorane malayana* Medvedev, 2019, male, holotype); 4–5 – *Dercetina bicolora* (Medvedev, 2018), male, holotype; 6–7 – *Dercetina bisbipunctata* (Medvedev, 2018), male, holotype. 1–4, 6 – habitus, dorsal view; 5, 7 – aedeagus, ventral view.

Рис. 1–7. Типовые экземпляры, габитус и эдеагус.

1 – *Apophyllia skalei* **nom. n.** (*Apophyllana thoracica* Medvedev, 2019, самка, голотип); 2 – *Aulacophora coffeae* (Hornstedt, 1788) (*Hoplasoma kelantana* Medvedev, 2019, самец, голотип); 3 – *Cassena collaris collaris* (Baly, 1879) (*Cneorane malayana* Medvedev, 2019, самец, голотип); 4–5 – *Dercetina bicolora* (Medvedev, 2018), самец, голотип; 6–7 – *Dercetina bisbipunctata* (Medvedev, 2018), самец, голотип. 1–4, 6 – габитус, вид сверху; 5, 7 – эдеагус, вид снизу.

Genus *Pseudocneorane* Medvedev et Romantsov, 2012

Pseudocneorane Medvedev et Romantsov, 2012: 77 (original description).

Comparative type material examined. *Metrioidea signatipennis*: 1♂, syntype (MNHN), “I. Viti” [w, h], “*Metrioidea signatipennis* Fairm” [w, h], “TYPE” [r, p], “Ex-Musaeo L. Fairmaire 1893” [vertically, p, w].

Comments. Medvedev and Romantsov [2012] described new genus and species *Pseudocneorane fulvicornis* from South Thailand. The description is accompanied with very good photos of habitus and aedeagus.

The genus *Metrioidea* was proposed by Fairmaire [1882] for *Metrioidea signatipennis* Fairmaire, 1882 from Fiji. Recently, the New Caledonian species of *Metrioidea*

Figs 8–12. Habitus of type specimens and aedeagus.

8 – *Galeruca sexcostata* Jacoby, 1904 (*Rhabdotilla rosti* Jacobson, 1911, sex unknown, syntype, photograph by Alexey Moseyko); 9–10 – *Galerucella pusilla* (Duftschmid, 1825) (*Galerucella flavidula* Reitter, 1913, male, syntype); 11 – *Menippus beeneni* Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012 (*Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* Medvedev, 2019, male, holotype); 12 – *Radymna rickmersi* (Weise, 1900) (*Galeruca reitteri* Havelka, 1958, male, holotype). 8–9, 11–12 – habitus, dorsal view; 10 – aedeagus, dorsal view.

Рис. 8–12. Типовые экземпляры, габитус и эдеагус.

8 – *Galeruca sexcostata* Jacoby, 1904 (*Rhabdotilla rosti* Jacobson, 1911, пол не определен, синтип, фотография А. Мосейко); 9–10 – *Galerucella pusilla* (Duftschmid, 1825) (*Galerucella flavidula* Reitter, 1913, самец, синтип); 11 – *Menippus beeneni* Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012 (*Pyrrhalta shaanxiana* Medvedev, 2019, самец, голотип); 12 – *Radymna rickmersi* (Weise, 1900) (*Galeruca reitteri* Havelka, 1958, самец, голотип). 8–9, 11–12 – габитус, вид сверху; 10 – эдеагус, вид сверху.

were revised by Beenen [2008b, 2013, 2017] who also depicted the aedeagus of *Metroidea signatipennis*. The occurrence of true *Metroidea* species is verified in Fiji and New Caledonia but probably they can be found in many parts of Australasia [Beenen, 2008b, 2013].

Jacoby [1884b] placed *Metroidea apicalis* Jacoby, 1884 from Sumatra into *Metroidea* with doubts. However, subsequent authors [e.g. Wilcox, 1973] accepted Jacoby's arrangement what revealed that three species from South Thailand, Peninsular Malaysia, Sumatra and Borneo are currently classified in *Metroidea*.

The genus *Metroidea* belongs to the Monoleptites group characterised by very long metatarsomere I and is close to species-rich genera *Monolepta* Chevrolat, 1836 and *Candezea* Chapuis, 1879. On the other hand, three species from Thailand, Malaysia and Indonesia have normal metatarsomere I and are close to *Itylus* Jacoby, 1904. The only available genus name for those species is *Pseudocneorane* and thus appropriate new combinations are proposed (see below).

**Genus *Pseudocneorane apicalis* (Jacoby, 1884),
comb. n.**

Metroidea apicalis Jacoby, 1884b: 226 (original description).

Nadrana bella Baly, 1886: 31 (original description).

Pseudocneorane fulvicornis Medvedev et Romantsov, 2012: 77 (original description), **syn. n.**

Type material. *Metroidea apicalis*: 1♀, syntype (RMNS), "Metroidea ? apicalis Jac." [b, h], "Dr. B. Hagen. Tandjong. Morawa. Serdang (N. O. Sumatra)." [w, p]; 1♂, syntype (MCZ, examined photo available at <http://mcbase.mcz.harvard.edu/SpecimenSearch.cfm>), "Dr. B. Hagen. Tandjong. Morawa. Serdang (N. O. Sumatra)." [w, p], "1st Jacoby Coll." [w, p], "Type [p], 18341 [r, h]"; "Metroidea ? apicalis, Jac. n. sp." [w, h].

Nadrana bella: 1 ex., syntype (BMNH), "Sum" [w, h], "Type" [w, p, round label with red collar], "Nadrana bella" [w, h], "Metroidea bella Baly Sumatra" [g, h], "Baly Coll." [w, p].

Pseudocneorane fulvicornis: not examined.

Type localities. *Metroidea apicalis*: "Serdang (East Sumatra)" (by the title). *Nadrana bella*: "Malacca, Tringarnee, Sumatra". *Pseudocneorane fulvicornis*: "Thailand, Phuket Island, near Karon, 7°50'52"N 98°18'20"E".

Distribution. Peninsular Malaysia, Indonesia (Sumatra) [Mohamedsaid, 2004], Thailand [Medvedev, Romantsov, 2012].

Comments. Although we did not examine holotype or paratypes of *Pseudocneorane fulvicornis*, the photograph and the description in the original publication are sufficient to propose *Pseudocneorane fulvicornis* Medvedev et Romantsov, 2012 as a junior synonym of *Metroidea apicalis* Jacoby, 1884.

Pseudocneorane grandis (Allard, 1889), **comb. n.**

Atysa grandis Allard, 1889: lxxix (original description).

Platyxantha robusta Jacoby, 1895: 110 (original description).

Metroidea borneensis Mohamedsaid, 1997: 154 (original description).

Type material. *Atysa grandis*: 2 ex., syntypes (MNHN), "Borneo" [w, h], "Ex-Musaeo E-ALLARD 1899" [w, h].

Metroidea borneensis: not examined.

Platyxantha robusta: 1♂, syntype (BMNH), "Type H. T." [white round label with red collar, p], "N. Guinea" [w, h], "Jacoby Coll. 1909-28a" [w, p], "Platyxantha robusta Jac. Type" [b, h]; 1 ex., syntype (BMNH), "N. Guinea" [w, h], "Jacoby Coll. 1909-28a" [w, p]; 1♂, possible syntype (MCZ), "Borneo" [w, h], "2nd Jacoby Coll." [w, p], "robusta Jac." [w, h], "Type. [p] 18353 [r, h]".

Type localities. *Atysa grandis*: "Bornéo". *Metroidea borneensis*: "Malaysia, Sarawak, Taman Negara Lambir". *Platyxantha robusta*: "New Guinea".

Distribution. Malaysia (Sarawak, Sabah) [Mohamedsaid, 1997, 2004].

Comments. As shown by Bezděk [2019], the type specimens of *Platyxantha robusta* were mislabelled and undoubtedly originated from Borneo.

Pseudocneorane molek (Mohamedsaid, 1994),
comb. nov.

Metroidea molek Mohamedsaid, 1994b: 26 (original description).

Type material. Not examined.

Type locality. "Kelantan, Jeram Pasu, Malaysia".

Distribution. Peninsular Malaysia [Mohamedsaid, 2004].

Radymna rickmersi (Weise, 1900)
(Fig. 12)

Diorhabda rickmersi Weise, 1900: 289 (original description).

Lochmaea ornaticollis Reitter, 1900: 231 (original description).

Galeruca (Haptoscelis) reitteri Havelka, 1958: 202 (original description), **syn. n.**

Pallasiola pamirica Mandl, 1968: 29 (original description).

Type material. *Diorhabda rickmersi*: 1 ex., syntype (MFNB), "Buchará Rickmers" [w, h], "Diorhabda Rickmersi m" [w, h], "ex. Coll. J. Weise" [w, p].

Lochmaea ornaticollis: 1♀, syntype (HNHM), "Buchará, Karatagh" [w, h], "Holotypus [red letters, p] 1900 Lochmaea ornaticollis Reitter" [w, h, label with red borders], "ornaticollis m. Buchará" [orange, h], "Diorhabda Rickmersi Wse. [h] Coll. Reitter [w, p]"; 1♀, syntype (HNHM), "Buchará, Karatagh" [w, h], "Paratypus [red letters, p] 1900 Lochmaea ornaticollis Reitter" [w, h, label with red borders], "Diorhabda Rickmersi Wse. [h] Coll. Reitter [w, p]".

Pallasiola pamirica: not examined.

Galeruca reitteri: 1♂, holotype (HNHM), "Safichadam [h] Süd-Turkestan K. Kuchler S. G. [p] 7.6. [h] 1913 [w, p]"; "Holotypus [red letters, p] 1958 Galeruca Haptoscelis reitteri Havelka" [w, h, label with red borders], "HOLO [h] TYPE [r, p]"; "Galeruca reitteri sp. n. ♂ [h] Det. Havelka [p] 1957 [w, p]".

Type localities. *Diorhabda rickmersi*: "Buchará". *Lochmaea ornaticollis*: "Buchará: Karatak". *Pallasiola pamirica*: "West-Pamir, Quellgebiet des Mühlenbaches Dszhailgan". *Galeruca reitteri*: "Süd-Turkestan: Safichadam".

Distribution. Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan [Beenen, 2010, 2014].

Comments. Havelka [1958] attributed his newly described species to *Galeruca* subgenus *Haptoscelis* Weise, 1886. This was followed in all subsequent publications [e.g. Wilcox, 1971; Beenen, 2010]. The holotype was examined and proved to belong to the genus *Radymna* Reitter, 1913. *Radymna rickmersi* is the only *Radymna*-species with hind corners of the pronotum being square. Besides the colouration of the upper parts and the elytral ridge from humerus to halfway the elytra are typical for *Radymna rickmersi*.

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